
Nature and Concept of Broken Homes: Implication for Academic Performance of Students and Youth Restiveness in Delta State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the effect of Broken Homes on the academic performance of students and their involvement in restive activities in Isoko North Local Government Area of Delta State. The sample for the study consist of 100 students and 50 teachers drawn from the 5 randomly selected schools in Isoko North Local Government Area. The data for the study was obtained through the administration of questionnaires. The procedure used for the analysis of data was simple percentage. The number of responses for each item in the questionnaire and the corresponding was computed from the analysis of data collected. The results showed that significant differences existed between the academic performance of students from single parent family and those from intact or stable family. The result also indicates that there is a significant difference in the interaction, attitude and behavioural patterns of students from broken homes and those from stable homes. And they indulge in youth restiveness and other social vices. Thus, school counsellors are to provide necessary assistance to students, especially those from single parent family.

KEYWORDS: Broken Home, Academic Performance, Youth Restiveness, Isoko North, Delta State-Nigeria

I. Introduction

Over the years investigations have been carried out on the effect of a broken home on the academic performance of students both in the primary, secondary and tertiary institutions. Researchers, teachers, counselling psychologists and school administrators within and outside Nigeria have shown considerable interest in this subject matter (Maimuna, 2018; Omoruyi, 2014; Dowd, 1997; Ichado, 1998; Ajila&Olutola, 2007; Luigi, 2010; Mosi, 2006; Nzewunnah, 1995; Uwaifo, 2008 and Okpevra, 2011). This is a severe case which has affected not just the educational aspect of the country, but also the economic, social as well as the political spheres of Nigeria.

Some of the findings of these researchers have shown that the causes of youth restiveness and student's poor performance at school is linked to the student's personal and institutional lifestyle. The personal aspect deals with the individual's intelligence, knowledge and ability while the institutional factor relates to the individual's background as it relates to family or parental influences and societal influences. Eweniyi (2005) of all the aforementioned factors, the parental influence has a greater hold on the student's emotional and psychological life.

Reviewed literature indicated that there is an awareness of the importance of the home environment or family on the student's academic performance. The home has a great influence on student's psychological, emotional, social and economic state. In the view of Ajila and Olutola (2007), the state of the home affects the individual since the parents are the first socializing agent in an individual's life. This is because the family background and context of a child affect his/her reaction to life situations and his level of performance. Although the school is responsible for the experiences that make up the individual's life during school periods,

yet parents and the individual's experience at home play tremendous roles in building the personality of the child and making the child what he is. Thus, Ichado (1998) concluded that the environment in which the student comes from can greatly influence his performance at school

Although, the home environment or family has been recognized as having a lot of influence on the academic performance of student Ajibola and Olutola (2007) previous studies have been concentrated on the area of the socioeconomic status of parents. Other aspects of the parental environment such as the structure of the family and its effect have been grossly neglected. Yet Ichado (1998) states that parent's constant disagreement affects children emotionally and this could lead to poor academic performance in school.

The family lays the psychosocial, moral and spiritual foundations in the overall development of the child. While the mother's significant role in this cannot be overemphasized, studies on the father - child relationship suggest that the presence of a father in the home influences significantly the development of a child (Agulanna, 1999). Thus, parenthood is a responsibility requiring the full cooperation of both parents who must ensure the total development of their offspring.

Suffice it to say that it is a common knowledge in Nigeria today that thousands of students come from families disrupted by cases of divorce and there are indications that this trend will continue to increase as our social behaviour remains unchecked. Going through a divorce is a very difficult situation to be in. Usually, it is what is happening between the parents that concerns most people. However hurtful divorce is on the couple that is going through it, the children are at the receiving end. The implications are not always obvious and do not always come to the surface immediately. But as the child develops and with the turn of events and situations around the child, these problems eventually surface.

Kelly (2000) says "children incorporate repertoires of angry, impulsive and violent behaviour into their own behaviour as a result of observing their parent's responses to frustration and rage". The increasing divorce rate may be linked to marriages based on financial or social status rather than love, one of the couples feeling that he/she got involved with the wrong partner, the increasing trend towards early parenthood without marital experience, financial and housing problems with the attendant early arrival of a body.

Ironically, adequate attention has not been given to the effects which broken homes may have had or may have, or better still may be having on the student's reaction to the new situation they find themselves. The home holds a very important position at the, base of any society. To a growing child, the home is the only world known, beyond this nothing exists. The home is the place where children are cared for and shown affection by their parents. It is assumed that the experience they share during the course of their upbringing has a profound influence on their personalities and academic performance.

The broken home may be as a result of crisis, conflicts, fighting and lack of understanding between the couple, which, when left unresolved may result in temporary or permanent separation of both parents. Hence the marriage vow often made at the altar with promise to love each other "for better or for worse as long as both shall live" becomes rhetoric resulting in the destruction of the academic, psychological and moral lives of the students.

Broken homes may be seen as a stressful situation for all participants even under the best circumstances Mosi (2006). The actual separation of parents may have been preceded by years of conflicts in the home or may come as a shock to all. After separation, there are changes that erupt, which will eventually disrupt the lives of all the members of the family especially the children. Some of these changes could be moving to a less expensive and poorly furnished home, finding new sources of income in order to meet up with the standard of living, in some cases the mother who in most cases gets the custody of the children may have to go to work for the first time or work longer hours for the sake of the children. The resultant effect of this is that the basic needs of the child, especially those that has to do with the emotions are abandoned. These children/students develop emotional instability, which inadvertently affect their academic performance in school. Children/student are naturally troubled by parent' disharmony. However, this may or may not affect the parent-child relationship, but in the long run affects their academic work in school and invariably propelled them into restive activities.

II. Research Questions

The following research questions will be carried out for the study in some selected secondary schools in Isoko North Local Government Area.

- 1) Is there any difference between the academic performance and involvement in youth restiveness of students from broken homes and students from a stable home?
- 2) Does a broken home have any effect on the student's relationship with other students in school?
- 3) Do students from broken homes constitute a social menace to school and the society by way of youth restiveness at large more than the student from stable homes?

III. Hypotheses

In pursuit of the research problems and to realize the objectives of this study, the basic ideas of this study is to look into some of these hypotheses and to test their validity.

- i. There is no significant difference between the academic performance and indulgence in youth restiveness of students from single parent families and those from two parent families.
- ii. There is no significant effect in the relationship between students from broken homes and those from stable homes.
- iii. There is no significant difference in the attitude and behavioural patterns of students from broken homes and those from table homes.

IV. The Concept of Marriage and Broken Homes.

Marriage has different meanings for different individuals and different societies at large. Many people today view marriage as an end point in personosocial development.

Marriage is a divine institution approved by God, which involves the legal union of man and woman who have agreed to live together as husband and wife, after completing the necessary processes (Cole 1993) Quoted in Onoawarie Edevbie (2005), http://www.waado.org/UrhoboCulture/marriage_family/edevbie_marriage.html.

Marriage is described by Aculfet *al*, as a social-cultural institution developed to meet human needs and assuring the perpetuation of what has been agreed as important and acceptable. They further described marriage as a procedure for meeting human needs; an organized means whereby the essential tasks of a society are carried out; a regulative organ which arranges individuals' activities into definite patterns (Aculf- et al, (1973), Eshleman (1975) and Eisenstradt (1968), quoted in Nnatu, (2004), P. 109.

Interestingly, marriage in Isokoland conforms to both the divine and traditional principles. For instance, in Isokoland, both monogamous and polygamous systems of marriage are prevalent: monogamy allows a man to make do with one woman, while, polygamy allows a man more than a wife - it could be two or more wives, depending on the man's socioeconomic capabilities. Polygamy is a product of interest and strength, therefore, polygamy in Isokoland, had both divine and traditional backings (Personal Communication with James Epini, Age 51, Businessman, interviewed at Ozoro, on March 30 2020).

Over the years, three forms of marriage have existed side by side. Marriage in Isokoland, as elsewhere, is a collective effort, not individual, that is concerned people, and especially family members of both sides are involved. Over the years, due to Christian penetration of Isokoland, the so-called white or church or Christian marriage has come to co-exist with the age-long traditional marriage. Another dimension, known as a court or legal marriage has also been adopted, and of all the systems of marriage, the most important and the most compulsory and most acceptable is the traditional marriage system. Even some good churches and good "courts" would insist on traditional marriage, first. (Epini Already Cited). Christian and legal systems of marriage gained entry into Isokoland, due to colonial cum Christian penetration in Nigeria and the changing patterns of social interaction:

However, marriage in Isokoland has some traditional processes, it should conform with. There were three distinctive patterns by which a man and a woman became united as husband and wife. These are *Aye-Sahoto* (Betrothal, adult's marriage- Ewareayeru (Dowry system) and *Aye-Uku* (inheritance). For marriage to be binding in Isokoland, it must be accompanied by payment of bride-price. The payment of bride-price is not optional, but compulsory. The dowry must be paid before the girl is escorted to her husband, at least,

traditionally speaking. In the precolonial era, the dowry or bride- price was in the form of a bag of cowries and recently it ranged from N200.00 to N300.00 Okpevra (2020).

One of the greatest legacies of marriage in Isokoland is that it brought two families and their extended families together, due to the involvement of parents and elders in all stages of marital arrangement. Through marriage, the family became a reality. The family has been viewed as the cornerstone of society and the most basic institution in all societies. The family performed the following functions: reproduction, socialization, socio- economic maintenance, sexual regulation and social control.

In the view of Olutola (2000) marriage is a universal institution which is recognized and respected all over the world. He further stressed that as a social institution, marriage is founded and governed by the social and religious norms of the society. Consequently, the sanctity of marriage is a well-accepted principle in the world. Marriage is the root of the family and of the society in general. The Great book (Holy Bible) states that “for this cause a man shall leave his father and mother and cling to his wife, and they two shall no longer be two but one flesh”. This has been a common phrase among people. They perhaps summoned up rational and spiritual impetus to the institution of marriage between couples. The marriage institution is a source of succour to all other institutions as it plays a distinct role in establishing and maintaining social- psychological stability with much guarantees of continuity.

According to Mosi (2006), young men and women should be encouraged to get married in order to fulfil one of the main functions of marriage (sexual needs) in the right way. There are powerful impulses to sexual behaviour in most human being and any organized society wishes to place this area of conduct under firm control. She further stated that basic to man’s needs are those of sexual expression and affection and while it is obvious that these are attainable outside the institution of marriage, it is also clear that completely unrestrained fulfilment of sexual desires could lead to a breakdown in the organization of the society.

Marriage is viewed by different individuals from different angles and from one epoch to another. For instance, some see marriage as just another of humans numerous secular contracts with great ephemeral potentialities. Others, especially among the Christian folk views marriage as a spiritual and heavenly knotting which is transcendental to the soul of man. Marriage has changed greatly over the years. It is now being viewed as a partnership of equals than as was the case in a relationship between dominant male and servicing female Ichado (1998).

Marriage stability should have been a non-issue if marriage is taken as Anderson (1982) puts it, that marriage was never intended to be a one side affair. It always takes two people to make a successful marriage. But unfortunately it takes only one through neglect or selfishness to spoil it. Thus he defined marriage as the first two party system of government ever devised emphasizing that continuity in marriage can only be guaranteed through a dual contribution of both parties involved in the institution itself.

V. The Concept of Broken Home

According to Luigi Boy (2010) the family is an essential factor for a human whole being, everything about a man, his background, and attitude, all of his achievements, his honour and dignity relies on the structure of the family a man lives in with. A family is composed of a father, a mother and their offspring bonded by their love for each other. Here in the modern age, a family could be two things, complete or broken. A broken family is believed to be the cause of a child’s mislead in life. Some people give it as the main reason for the rebellious and unclear acts of children, which invariably lead to youth restiveness.

There are different opinions about broken homes. Different scholars view the concept of broken homes from various angles. Divorce (an aspect of broken home) is defined as the dissolution of marriage by law and separation, which is another form of broken home has been defined as the living apart of husband and wife or by order of the law court OmeZeghian G.E. (1995). A home is said to be broken when the spouses or parents are separated. A woman in her marital home suddenly sees herself as one suffering and can no longer put up with the situation in the home. She sees her matrimonial home as a place of emotional and psychological torture, physical abuse and a hell on earth. She then feels she cannot stay there anymore, on the other hand, some men quit their homes when they feel they can no longer put up with the behaviour of their wives. When a marriage is dissolved the man and the woman no longer have any obligation to each other and there is no bond of marriage.

Occurrences like death, desertion, divorce or separation are all forms of broken homes. Informal desertion occurs in many under-privileged families when a parent simply abandons the family. Some of these aspects of broken homes are backed by law. Divorce or broken home laws vary from country to country and from state to state. In some states, for instance, the law prohibits divorce. The only situation that warrants that is the case of death. Likewise, some religious institutions forbid divorce. e.g. The Roman Catholic Church. However, a divorce can be granted if one spouse has been found guilty of a violation of his/her marital obligation.

However, the effects of broken homes on students cannot be over-emphasized. Conclusively, from the above analysis, it can be deduced that divorce brings about the family crisis because the decision to become separated usually results in one form of family crisis or another. Hence, persistent failure to attain the purpose of marriage often constitutes marriage, family or home breakdown.

VI. Various Dimensions of Broken Homes

Broken homes or marital dissolution is a social problem relating to the institution of marriage or the family. Structurally, a family is either broken or intact. A broken family in this context is one that is not structurally intact for various reasons of the death of a parent, divorce, separation, desertion and illegitimacy in which case the family was never completed. (Conkline 1996). The following dimensions of broken homes are as explained by Mosi (2006).

Marital dissolution is an omnibus concept which encapsulates circumstances in which a marriage is terminated or dissolved. Divorce can also be described as a legal termination or dissolution of a legal or customary marriage by a court or an appropriate agency. Separation as it relates to marital dissolution has two connotations. First, it refers to a circumstance where a legally married couple by their own choice chooses to live apart from one another. Though they are legally married, the court outlines the conditions under which the concerned partners would leave. Secondly separation could result in a situation where one party, particularly the woman not wanting to put up with the ills of the marriage decides to separate from her partner. Although there are some cases of male separation from their spouse without any reason too. Dissertation refers to a situation where one of the partners abandons the other spouse. Annulment is the legal termination of a marital relationship which may not have been legal or the voiding of a legal marriage on account of its violation of marital laws.

VII. Causes of Broken Home

In the past, broken home in an average Nigerian society was minimal and the consequential effects of the products of such marriage have been negligible because of the setting of the traditional African society. However, with increased urbanization and westernization of our culture coupled with the idea of women's liberation, broken homes in the average Nigerian society becomes comparable to what obtains in the western world.

Ajibola and Olutola (2007) explains that divorce in our society today is alarmingly on the increase. And the question that bothers everyone is, "is it the wishes of couples to marry only to separate a few months after", if not, what is actually responsible for this trend? They further stated that women account mostly for marriage breakup. This is because they have more to give in order to build a happy and solid home. When a woman fails in her obligations, her man starts to look elsewhere for the fulfilment of his desire, this can definitely lead to a broken home.

There are many things that lead to broken homes. The commonest of all is the lack of love between husband and wife. Some marriages are contracted without genuine mutual understanding between the couples Mosi (2006). A good example is when a man impregnates a lady and he is forced to marry her. In such marriage of convenience, genuine love is almost lacking. Many young adults get pregnant even before they complete their primary or secondary education. A marriage contracted as a result of premarital pregnancy is very likely to break up. This is because either one or both of the couple are too young to understand the involvement in marriage. -

Infidelity and adultery are other reasons for breakdown in marriage. Moral misbehaviour on the other hand has deteriorated in our society so much so that some married men and women engaged in extramarital affairs with impunity. Wife battering could also lead to broken homes as some men feel that beating and abusing their wives is the best way to attain superiority in the marriage. Olutola (2000) states that sterility or barrenness on the part of the wife or husband could bring separation where the couples are unable to give birth to children. As a result of this there may be interference and pressures from the extended families of both spouses and even from friends. The incompatibility of the blood group of a couple could also lead to separation.

Economic standing in a family plays an important role in Nigerian marriages. In the traditional Nigerian society, the man used his wife or wives as the case may be, with his children to improve his economy, especially, in the area of farming. But today, the reverse is the case. Nowadays a man uses his economic might to maintain his wife, children and his home in general. When the man is unable to meet the needs of his family, one of the resultant effect is a broken home. Increasing emphasis on materialism in this era further worsens this situation. Related to this is the issue of a man not wanting his wife to work.

Luigi Boy (2010) noticed that most husbands of today want the financial assistance their wives can give, yet they frown at the idea of their wives going to work at the expense of taking care of the home and the children. This sometimes brings problems and conflict between husband and wife and if not properly handled eventually leads to a broken home. However, no responsible man is expected to frown at his wife going to work. But frowning may actually be permitted when the woman begins to feel superior, financially intoxicated, morally lax, unfaithful, and not submissive to the man and tends to overlook her domestic responsibilities. The exhibition of any of these ugly attitudes undermined the general marriage principles that the man remains the head of the home no matter his status or financial position.

Ill health sometimes leads to broken homes in the Nigeria society today. This is a situation where the partner becomes insensitive to what the society thinks of him or her but decides to abandon his/her spouse due to ill health. Unfortunately, the society in which we live today is hostile to an invalid or a handicapped person. The result of this is that when a marriage partner becomes an invalid either through sickness or accident, the other partner abandons him/her.

Eweniyi (2010) has also identified lack of communication as one of the causes of separation in a marriage. In many marriages, communication is far from a complete integration of all attitudes and feelings. One of the partners in most cases the woman, may not dare to say exactly what he/she feels until anger forces hidden feelings and attitudes to the surface. The spouse cannot use the negative information effectively because hostile tones often produce defensiveness. Mosi (2006) has also observed that bias interference by parents is another factor that causes broken homes. Some parents interfere in the family life of young couples and as a result break the young marriage. Parent-in-laws out of greed and selfishness contribute to the young couple's marital dissolution because either of the partners feel that the other is not living up to expectation. She further stated that children also support the separation of their parents. There are cases where the children actively encourage parental separation. Most commonly found in families where alcoholism and physical abuse becomes a long-term problem.

Matrimonial Decree of (1970) in Nigeria stipulates grounds upon which broken homes could rest upon. (1.) Adultery - which is the engagement in sexual intercourse with a spouse with another person outside the marriage. (2.) Unreasonable conduct which may tend to make the marriage hell on earth for the petitioner (3.) Desertion or intended separation for a continuous period of at least one year. (4.) Two years separation coupled with the consent of the respondent to dissolution.

According to Olutola (2007) frigidity or impotence is a very sensitive factor/cause of broken homes. This refers to the functional inability of the man to perform sexual intercourse in spite of sexual desire and the presence of intact genital organs. Frigidity could be total or partial, but whatever its degree, it is not a disease entity itself, rather it is a symptom of the manifestation of underlying neurotic conflict and as such can be traced to a number of psychological mechanisms. Where there is a cause of frigidity or impotence in a marriage, disintegration or marital dissolution becomes inevitable.

VIII. The Effect of Broken Homes on Academic Performance of Students

The effects of broken homes on students vary from one situation to the other and it has caused a lot of menace in the society. Maimuna (2018) confirms that there are many things that divorce does to a family and particularly to the child in the family. These effects are rarely positive or helpful depending on the family's prior situation. A broken home has many negative effects on the psychological, social, emotional and educational aspects of a student's life. As earlier mentioned in the introduction a child may not show initially how he or she feels about the separation of his/her parents, but the true feelings of that child eventually surface. One of the psychological effect of a broken home on students' academic performance is depression. Children who experience marital conflict during their childhood are said to suffer depression and other psychological disorders as students, which invariably propelled them into restive activities.

Socially, most children from broken homes often feel unconnected to their peers Imogie (2002). They feel unable to make or maintain friendships and complains a lot of their peers. In numerous studies over the past four decades, children from broken homes have been reported to be more aggressive and impulsive and engage in antisocial behaviours compared with matching samples of never divorced children. These students also end up cutting and failing classes. They are likely to be neck-deep in such nefarious activities as an Internet fraud / scam, referred to in local parlance as "Yahoo Boys" and "G Boys". They are also actively involved in such vices as rape, cultism and armed robbery and lately ritual killings.

One of the greatest hardship that faces students from broken homes is feeding. Mosi (2006) has this to say, "in order to benefit fully from life around them in terms of communication and play, a child must be adequately nourished and healthy". Malnutrition could lead to a permanent reduction in the number of brain cells despite any subsequent nutritional improvement. Mosi further stressed that when children are well fed from infancy, they grow up to be healthy adults with a well-built body and they can learn faster and are clever. On the other hand, if they have been poorly fed from infancy, it affects their performance at school.

Lovell (1993) notes that the instability of the home is another major effect of broken homes on students' academic performance and their involvement in youth restiveness. Unfavourable home condition to a great extent affects the emotions of the students who try to stabilize themselves when they are supposed to be learning at school. This inadvertently leads to failure for such students.

Nwankwo A. O. (1992) children from broken homes who live with either father or mother are presented with a ton of unfortunate encounters. The father who sees ex-wife as an issue to him may move the animosity to the children. The father sees the evil conduct of the child as being teleguided by their mother, consequently he uses such comments "like mother like little girl, no big surprise your mother couldn't remain, I realize you took after your mother and so on then again, if the child or student remains with the mother, the circumstance isn't in an ideal situation. She moves her complaints to her ex-husband to the youngster who never applied for the messed up home circumstance. Comments "like father, similar to child, you are your father's duplicate in conduct or did your father send you, this house won't contain us and so on are regularly utilized on such children. Such comments influences the children both mentally and genuinely in this way bringing about the helpless scholastic execution.

Peretomode (2007) and Iguana (2005) depose that effects of a broken homewithstudents, especially at the adolescent stage promotes indiscipline, hooliganism and juvenile delinquency. Delinquency and conduct disorder leads to inefficiency in academic performance because they are exposed to bad experiences or influences in the society. Socially maladjusted students manifest certain traits such as pick pocketing, rioting, fighting, prostitution, cheating, lying, habitual truancy, lateness to school, hypersensitivity. Any student who manifest all these finds, it difficult to fit into a classroom or school situations.

Against the backdrop of the above, students from broken homes, therefore finds it difficult to get on well with their fellow students in the school. They are sometimes aggressive, suspicious of people in terms of communication and play and this could affect their academic performance because they find it difficult to ask their fellow students to put them through where they could not meet up their classes or periods, they prefer to stay alone.

The effects of broken home on the student's academic performance are inexhaustible. Some of these students who have the opportunity and financial assistance to be educated readily prefer to learn a trade so as to

become self-supporting early in life. Most of them end up learning trades that are not properly coordinated and at the end they become uneducated, their learning period is not completed and they get involved or indulge in criminal activities.

In conclusion, however, it is important to note that parent-child separation as a result of broken homes or other factors that necessitate this has an adverse effect on the students' capacity of achievement. The separation experiences may be severe and harmful depending on the degree of the relationship between them.

IX. Remedies to the Problem of Broken Homes

The issue of incessant broken homes as a causal factor in the origin, growth and development of restiveness and delinquent behaviours among school students has often been spoken of by concerned persons and institutions. It has been proven that the poor social, cultural, religious and emotional climates of their homes are probably one of the most important factors in the establishment of deviant traits and its subsequent attitudinal manifestations. Odeunmi (1990) noted that most delinquents tend to be found more often than not in homes experiencing separation, divorce, death or prolonged absence of a parent. To that extent, it is, therefore, necessary for the government and parents to handle the issue of family stability more serious. Teenage pregnancy should be discouraged in the society and marriage should be contracted for only couples who are physically; intellectually, morally and financially prepared. Divorce cases should be discouraged by all means, whether the marriages were contracted under the law, customary or religious platforms.

Mosi (2006) noted that there should be a sense of maturity and adequate preparation for intending couples before marriage. Intended couples should undergo a period of courtship when they can understand themselves better before marriage. They should also be made to attend marriage seminars and marriage counselling for proper guidance. After the marriage rites has been performed, the couple should be faithful to each other and ensure mutual understanding, love, sincerity and truth among them.

The importance of communication in any relationship cannot be overemphasized. There should be a constant network of communication between the couples in order to have a successful home. The man should see the woman as a weaker vessel. As it is written in the bible that out of the man's ribs the woman was made. She should be treated with care and a lot of patience. The woman on the other hand should be submissive to her husband. They should constantly remember the vows they made during their marriage. The educational differences, religious, cultural and traditional prejudice should be over looked.

Iguana (2006) advised that parents, caregivers, teachers and other adults should take up the responsibility of always talking to children from broken homes. A lot of times it is realized that broken homes affects the students tremendously. Also get their grades from their teachers and sit down and talk positively to them about it.

In conclusion, therefore having examined the work of various writers on the causes and effects of broken homes on children and students, the work intends to find out the effects of broken homes on the academic performance of students and indulgence in restive activities in Isoko North Local Government Area of Delta State. It also intends to state possible solutions to the problems of broken homes.

It is obvious from the above that many individuals from different societies have different views about the marriage institution. Broken home is probably as old as marriage itself. Broken homes may be due to various causes as enumerated above. Children from broken homes are made to bear the negative effects of the situation in which they find themselves, that is their parents not living together. They are more likely to face problems such as lack of proper care in terms of inadequate school materials, fees and irregular attendance in school, little or no time may be given to private studies after school hours.

It is imperative for parents to know that broken homes affect their children more than anything, therefore they should avoid it. They should try to show maximum affection, attention, recognition and approval to their children. They should also take interest in observing the activities in which their children engage in at their leisure time. When corrections are given at an earlier period or stage in a child's life far reaching rewards are often recorded.

Materials and Method: The method and procedure adopted in carrying out the research are based on the following

- i. Design of study ii. Population iii. Sample and sampling technique iv. Instrumentation
v. Validity and reliability vi. Method of data collection vii. Method of data analysis

Design of the Study

The design is a survey using the questionnaire to elicit facts that will be computed and decisions will be reached.

Population of the Study

The focus of the study is all the secondary school students in Isoko North Local Government Area of Delta State. The local government has a total of 17 schools with a total population of 7,822 students.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A simple random sampling technique was used to select five secondary schools in the area. They are

	Name of Schools	Boys	Girls	Teachers	Total
A	Notre Dame College, Ozoro	10	10	10	30
B	Owhelogbo Grammar School, Owhelogbo	10	10	10	30
C	James Welsh Grammar School, Emevor	10	10	10	30
D	Otor-owhe Grammar School, Otor-owhe	10	10	10	30
E	Oyede Grammar School, Oyede	10	10	10	30
	Total	50	50	50	150

Instrumentation

The main material used is the questionnaire. The questionnaire is a list of questions or statement to which individuals are asked to respond in writing. The response may range from a check mark of either Yes or No, Agree, Disagree or Strongly Disagree etc. Two types of questionnaire were prepared, the first questionnaire was for the teachers while the second type was for the student. The questionnaire was designed to seek information about student's interest in school, parental care and attitude towards their academics and parental provision of basic school materials.

The type of questionnaire used is the Likert Scale questionnaire in which four options are provided, e.g. Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The number of items used is 15. The numerical rating scale was also used. The point attached is one point for each question.

Validity and Reliability

The validity of the questionnaire was ascertained by the structure of the questionnaire was designed to collect valid and reliable information about the views of the respondents. The questionnaire was scrutinized, corrected by the authors before it was finally used. The instrument is found to be reliable because it measured the view of the students and teachers in the secondary schools.

Method of Data Collection

The questionnaire was distributed to the areas concerned by the authors and collected back after they have been answered.

Method of Data Analysis

The method used in analysing the information were based on frequency score, simple percentage and tables. The responses in each of the items in the question score one point. So in finding the percentage, it is the frequency of each specific number over the total number of frequencies multiplied by 100. That is;

$$\text{Percentage} = \frac{\text{frequency of each No.}}{\text{Total No. of frequency}} \times 100$$

Total No. of frequency

Analysis of Data and Discussion of Result

The data are presented in tables. The simple frequency is used and the percentages are employed in providing answers to the research question formulated above. The results are presented as they relate to the hypotheses.

Hypothesis I

There is no significant difference between the academic performance of students from single parent families and those from two parent families.

Table 1: Difference in the academic performance of students and indulgence in youth restiveness from single parents and two parents.

Responses	Frequency of Response	Percentage
Strongly agree	12	8%
Agree	18	12%
Disagree	81	54%
Strongly disagree	39	26%
Total	150	100%

The data in table I indicates that there is a significant difference between the academic performance of students from single parent families and those from a two parent family. The calculated percentage of the number of disagree is greater than the other response given. Thus the null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant effect in the relationship between students from broken homes and those from stable homes.

Table 2: Difference in the interaction of students from broken homes and those from stable homes.

Responses	Frequency of Response	Percentage
Strongly agree	40	26.6%
Agree	68	45.4%
Disagree	19	12.6%
Strongly disagree	23	15.4%
Total	150	100%

Table 2 shows that there is a significant effect in the relationship between students from broken homes and those from stable homes.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the attitude and behavioural patterns of students from broken homes and those from table homes.

Table 3: Difference in the attitude and behavioural patterns of students from broken homes and those from table homes.

Responses	Frequency of Response	Percentage
Strongly agree	73	48.7%
Agree	43	28.7%
Disagree	14	9.3%
Strongly disagree	20	13.3%
Total	150	100%

Table 3 shows that there is a significant difference in the attitude and behavioural patterns of students from broken homes and those from stable homes.

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study indicate that there is a significant difference between the academic performance of students from single parent families and those from two parent families. The study also shows differences in the interaction of students from broken homes and those from stable homes. The findings also

agreed with the conclusion of (Nzewunnah, 1995) that there is a significant difference in the attitude and behavioural patterns of students from broken homes and those from table homes.

This finding could be explained by the fact that life in a single parent family can be traumatic and children brought up in such family structure often suffer some emotional problems such as lack of warmth, love and disciplinary problems, which may hinder their academic performance. On the other hand children raised in a two parent family structure are often stable emotionally and they suffer emotional problems, thereby making them less anxious in the pursuit of their academic work.

Furthermore, the critical analysis of the findings also reveals that this situation may not be true at all times since there are some children in single parent family structures who are well brought up and who still perform academically better than children from two parent family structure. There are instances of students who are from a single parent family and still top their class. This situation may however be attributed to other factors inherent in the personality of the child. Whatever the result, parental separation tends to affect younger children more than adolescents who are the subject of this study. However, early childhood problems may have a negative impact on later life development.

It should also be mentioned here that the presence of other adults in single parent household may bring some positive influence on the degree of tension that may be suffered by children from such background. Also the cultural practice in Nigeria, which allows support for widows, widowers and other categories of single parents helps to reduce the inconsiderable terms of the negative effect of single parenthood. In a Nigerian single parent family, some of the functions of the absent parent may be sufficiently taken over by the members of the extended family, friends and neighbours.

Summary of Research

This research work was carried out on the effects of broken homes on academic performance and the indulgence in restive activities of students in Isoko North Local Government Area of Delta State. The research took place in five secondary schools of the same local government area. The authors used a questionnaire to collect their data and the responses were worked out on simple percentage and table analysis.

Findings

The findings reveal that there is a significant difference between the academic performance and the involvement of youth restiveness of student from single parent family and students from a two parent family. The study also indicates that there is a significant effect on the interaction of students from broken homes and those from stable homes. The findings also show differences in the attitude and behavioural patterns of students from broken homes and those from stable homes.

Conclusion

The result of this study is very impressive. As a matter of fact, when love is not shown to a child when he or she is young, such child grows up not loving someone. Children do not easily outgrow their experience, especially vivid emotional crisis. Children from broken homes often experience reactions of shock and depression, anger and despair, they become more quarrelsome, restless, restive and bored at school. Children that lack fatherly or motherly love and affection, which impede academic progress, lack of moral support from both parents live in fear and anxiety and lack financial support from both parents.

They are less respectful, insulting their parents, teachers and even feel inferior to others, being cheated in the community. The home gives the child a feeling of security that grows from affection. In a good home, the child knows that his/her affection does not have to be earned, that no matter how he/she misbehave or how inept he/she may be in learning, his/her parents will stand by him/her if and when in trouble will make allowance for his/her mistakes and will sacrifice their comfort if necessary. However, parents should not fail to realize the problems they create for their children's future, they tend to ruin the society at large. This study and others have shown that growing up in a broken home, especially, without the father can permanently restructure and rewire the brain and can create more aggression and anger in children. Female children on their part when raised in broken homes without a father's input are likely to be sexually promiscuous and also more likely get divorced.

More often than not like the saying goes “like mother like daughter”. A greater percentage of teen births happen in homes of single mothers, even juvenile delinquents and runaways are raised in single parent homes.

X. Implication of the Study to Education

The following can be said to be the implication of the study to the educational system. The role of parents and family in the academic performance of the child is inherited psychologically and socially from one’s parents. Children team themselves easily and learning persists into adulthood. It then means that in the socialization of the child and for the maintenance of social order, the authority’s behaviour of parents in the authority inception period is highly functional. The well-adjusted child will perceive his parent child relationship as happy and close the theoretical idea.

XI. Recommendation

From the foregoing therefore, the following recommendation has been made by the authors.

1. Government, private organization and individuals concerned with the business of education should endeavour to address the obstacles hindering effective academic performance of students. This can be done by developing achievement motivation in students through achievement motivation training
 2. There is the need for the recognition of individual differences in students and the need to deal with them accordingly. Counsellors should provide the necessary assistance and psychological support for students from single parent family so as to overcome their emotional problems.
 3. There is also the need to keep enlightening the parents on the importance of the home structure on the life of the children. This is necessary so that parents can understand the implications and consequences of parental separation and thus mobilize all resources to curtail the problems arising from the situation.
 4. The counselling department should make out time to visit religious places and educate them in the sense of maturity and adequate preparation for intending couples before marriage. Intending couples should be made to undergo a period of courtship to understand themselves before marriage. The importance of communication cannot be over-emphasized. There should be communication between couples at all times in order to have a successful home.
 5. Finally, the ministry of education should employ functional school councils in all institutions of learning, especially in higher primary schools and secondary schools and adequate supervision be put in place to ensure the provision of necessary guidance services to students.
- Thus it is imperative that parents should do well to avoid divorce and the eventual broken for the sake of the children and their future.

XII. Suggestion for Further Study

Further study should be carried out on this topic in other local government areas of Delta state and in Nigeria as a whole. The researchers should dwell exhaustively on the areas not tackled in this study such as the psychological effects of broken homes on students and how broken homes can either make or mar the future of individuals. This will help to validate or refute some or all of our findings.

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